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**OUTPATIENT DIAGNOSIS AND MANAGEMENT OF IRON DEFICIENCY
ANEMIA IN WOMEN OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE: A CLINICAL STUDY IN
KAZAKHSTAN**

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Abstract. *Iron deficiency anemia remains one of the most common forms of anemia among women of reproductive age, especially in regions with limited access to specialized healthcare. This article presents the results of a clinical study conducted in the Akmola and Almaty regions of Kazakhstan from 2020 to 2024, involving 294 women aged 18 to 45 years. The aim of the study was to determine the prevalence of IDA and evaluate the effectiveness of outpatient therapy using oral iron preparations. The study included laboratory diagnostics (hemoglobin, ferritin), assessment of clinical symptoms, and treatment tolerability. The results demonstrated high treatment effectiveness: most patients showed improvement in laboratory parameters and clinical condition. Iron preparations were well tolerated, and adverse effects were minimal. The findings confirm the need to implement regular screening for iron deficiency in outpatient gynecological practice.*

Keywords: *iron deficiency anemia, ferritin, hemoglobin, oral therapy, women of reproductive age, gynecology, Kazakhstan, screening, anemia treatment.*

Relevance. Iron deficiency anemia is one of the most significant problems in reproductive medicine. According to the World Health Organization, more than 30% of women of reproductive age worldwide suffer from anemia, and this figure continues to rise [1,2]. Iron deficiency adversely affects fertility, pregnancy outcomes, childbirth, and the postpartum period, increasing the risk of obstetric complications and perinatal pathology [3,4].

In Kazakhstan, according to the World Bank, anemia was observed in 30.5% of women of reproductive age in 2023 [2,10]. In northern regions such as the Akmola region, the prevalence of IDA among women of reproductive age is approximately 28–30%, which is comparable to national indicators [5–7]. In southern regions, including the Almaty region, local studies report a prevalence of about 23–25% [8,9].

Women often first consult a gynecologist with complaints associated with IDA, such as fatigue, dizziness, and heavy menstrual bleeding. This makes the gynecologist a key specialist in early

diagnosis and treatment of iron deficiency, especially in regions with high birth rates and limited access to specialized medical care.

Thus, studying the prevalence of IDA in different regions of Kazakhstan and evaluating the effectiveness of therapy in outpatient gynecological practice is of significant scientific and practical importance.

Aim of the Study. The aim of this study was a comprehensive investigation of iron deficiency anemia in women of reproductive age in selected regions of Kazakhstan—Akmola and Almaty regions—during the period from 2020 to 2024.

The study was aimed at determining the prevalence of iron deficiency and anemia in this population, identifying the main clinical manifestations and risk factors, and evaluating the effectiveness of outpatient iron therapy used in gynecological practice.

An additional objective was to analyze the tolerability of different iron formulations and to assess the dynamics of laboratory and subjective indicators during treatment, in order to substantiate the most rational approaches to IDA correction in outpatient settings.

Materials and Methods. This study was conducted from January 2020 to March 2024 in outpatient settings, including antenatal clinics and polyclinics in the Akmola and Almaty regions. Both public and private healthcare institutions participated.

Women aged 18 to 45 years presenting with symptoms characteristic of IDA—chronic fatigue, reduced physical endurance, palpitations, dizziness, and/or heavy menstrual bleeding—were included. The diagnosis of IDA was confirmed by laboratory findings: hemoglobin levels below 120 g/L in non-pregnant women and below 110 g/L in pregnant women, along with serum ferritin levels below 30 ng/mL.

Patients with comorbid conditions that could affect hematological parameters (such as chronic inflammatory diseases, vitamin B12 deficiency, or folate deficiency) were excluded. Women in the second and third trimesters of pregnancy were also excluded.

A total of 294 women were included in the study. Each participant underwent a comprehensive evaluation including medical history, clinical examination, laboratory blood tests, and symptom assessment using standardized questionnaires.

To assess anemia severity, a complete blood count was performed, including hemoglobin, hematocrit, and mean corpuscular volume (MCV). Serum ferritin was additionally measured as a key indicator of iron stores. When necessary, transferrin levels and soluble transferrin receptors were also evaluated to уточнить характер железодефицита.

Treatment was carried out using oral iron preparations, primarily ferrous sulfate (Fe^{2+}) and iron(III)-hydroxide polymaltose complex (Fe^{3+}). Dosage was individualized based on anemia severity, typically ranging from 100 to 200 mg of elemental iron per day. Vitamin C was recommended to enhance absorption and reduce adverse effects. The duration of therapy ranged from 8 to 12 weeks, corresponding to the minimum course required to replenish iron stores and correct anemia.

To evaluate treatment effectiveness, follow-up assessment was conducted 8–12 weeks after therapy initiation. Changes in laboratory parameters (hemoglobin, ferritin) and subjective improvement in fatigue, endurance, and quality of life were assessed. The frequency and severity of adverse effects were also recorded.

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 26. Quantitative variables before and after treatment were compared using paired Student's t-test or the Wilcoxon signed-rank test depending on data distribution. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results. The study included 294 women of reproductive age (18–45 years), with a mean age of 31.2 ± 6.7 years. At baseline, all participants had confirmed iron deficiency with reduced hemoglobin and ferritin levels.

The mean baseline hemoglobin level was 10.4 ± 0.6 g/dL, corresponding to mild to moderate anemia. The mean serum ferritin level was 9.2 ± 3.5 ng/mL, indicating significant iron deficiency.

Clinical symptoms most commonly reported by the participants included fatigue (83.3%), reduced physical endurance (74%), palpitations and dyspnea on exertion (68%), and menorrhagia (approximately 60%).

After 10–12 weeks of iron therapy, significant improvements were observed in both laboratory and clinical parameters. The mean hemoglobin level increased to 12.6 ± 0.4 g/dL ($p < 0.001$), with more than 87% of patients achieving normal or borderline values. Serum ferritin levels also increased significantly, reaching 27.4 ± 6.2 ng/mL ($p < 0.001$), indicating restoration of iron stores.

In addition to laboratory improvements, a marked reduction in fatigue was noted. According to the visual analog scale (VAS, 1–10), the mean fatigue score decreased from 7.4 ± 1.3 before treatment to 3.1 ± 1.1 after therapy ($p < 0.001$), reflecting a substantial improvement in overall well-being.

Overall clinical effectiveness, defined as simultaneous improvement in hemoglobin, ferritin levels, and subjective condition, was achieved in 89.1% of patients. A partial response was observed in 10.9% of cases and was primarily associated with treatment interruption or poor adherence.

Adverse effects were observed in 9.5% of patients, mainly mild gastrointestinal symptoms (epigastric discomfort, constipation). In fewer than 1% of cases, a change of iron formulation was required.

Iron(III)-hydroxide polymaltose complex demonstrated better tolerability with comparable efficacy to ferrous iron.

Conclusion

1. The prevalence of Iron deficiency anemia among women of reproductive age in the Akmola and Almaty regions ranges from 23% to 30%.
2. Oral iron therapy is effective and safe in outpatient gynecological practice.
3. Routine screening of ferritin and hemoglobin is recommended, especially in high-risk regions.

Practical Recommendations

- Include ferritin and hemoglobin screening in standard evaluation for patients with heavy menstruation and fatigue
- Train gynecologists and general practitioners in IDA diagnosis and management
- Improve treatment adherence through educational programs and monitoring of therapy effectiveness

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